

INTERNATIONAL INVESTMENT LAW AND ITS CONNECTION WITH ECONOMIC RELATIONSHIPS

Abduvokhidova Saodat

Tashkent State University of law

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8054703>

The attribution of international investment law as an autonomous branch of international economic law is predicated on the existence of criteria that are universally acknowledged by the theory and practice of modern international law in the process of the growth of new industries, sub-sectors, and institutions. This decision was reached as a result of the presence of these criteria in the development of new industries, sub-sectors, and institutions. The numerous organizations, principles, norms, and standards that pertain to the legal regime of international investment are included under the umbrella of the system of international investment law. However, it is far too early to talk of the establishment of a worldwide investment law that functions in accordance with universal legal principles and standards.

The sources of international investment law each have their own distinctive characteristics, which are manifested in the congruent mix and interplay of conventional legal norms and "soft law" legal standards, the latter of which have an advisory function. According to the findings of an international legal examination of international bilateral, regional, and multilateral treaties regulating foreign investment, the overarching goal of these agreements is to strengthen the framework of international investment law. Although A. G. Bogatyrev was the first person to justify the independence of investment law as a set of principles, norms, and rules controlling activities involving foreign investment on the territory of the host state in the early 1990s, the concept of investment law as a whole has been around for much longer. It took a great deal of time before this idea gained what might be called widespread support. There are now a substantial number of conventions and institutions that are directly connected to this field, which is fairly significant. V. M. Shumilov is of the same perspective, and he identifies investment law as a branch of international economic law along with, for example, international trade law and international financial law. G. M. Velyaminov took a rather fresh approach to researching this topic by drawing on the recent advancements that have been made in the theory and practice of international law. His viewpoint is that international property law, which is a subfield of international economic law, is the appropriate location for the study of international investment law.

In spite of the substantial amount of experience that has been accumulated in the field of legal regulation of foreign investment, there is still no suitable mechanism for the required international legal regulation. This, as I. Z. Farkhutdinov correctly believes, can be explained, to a certain extent, by the topic's lack of adequate development. A thorough and analytical approach to research within the recently distinguished field of public international law and the system of private international law can be of assistance in this regard.

There have already been several attempts to justify a specialized international investment law that have been published in the scholarly literature. The well-known English scientist George Schwarzenberger is credited with penning the first significant work on the issues surrounding the international legal regulation of foreign investment. Schwarzenberger published the monograph "Foreign Investment and International Law" in London in the year 1969. In this work, the author did not single out any particular international investment law. In 1994,

Cambridge saw the publication of a second study that was quite analogous to the first and was specifically devoted to the international legal elements of foreign investment. Professor M. Sornarajah, who teaches at the National University of Singapore, is the one responsible for producing this scholarly work. This work lends credence to the notion that international investment law should be treated as a distinct topic of the legal profession.

As for modern domestic legal literature, the question of the place of the legislation on foreign investment is solved unequivocally: almost all authors dealing with this issue refer the legal norms of the legislation on foreign investment to the branch of private international law, to the sub-branch of property rights in private international law. This solution provides an unambiguous answer to the question of where the legislation on foreign investment should be placed. The norms of national legislation directly and directly regulate investment relations. This means that a direct method of regulating relations with a foreign element is applied, rather than a conflict method, which is the main or predominant one, according to the majority of scientists who are specialists in private international law. This is the case because the norms of national legislation are directly derived from international law. As M. M. Boguslavsky points out, the legal structure of contacts involving foreign investments is such that they require a unique two-level legal regulation. This regulation must be a combination of international legal norms and domestic (national) legal standards.

When asked about the fundamentals of international investment law, V. M. Shumilov cited the following as some of the most important ones: freedom to export investments; investment protection; non-damage by investments to the economy of the host country; prevention of the expropriation (nationalization) of foreign investments without appropriate compensation; subrogation; elimination of double taxation; non-discrimination; most favored nation; granting national treatment; and other such protections and privileges.

One can designate the difficulties of independence (sovereignty) and at the same time the interdependence of states in the region under investigation as new trends in the legal support of international investment relations. This is because these problems are considered to be new trends. When viewed within the framework of globalization, the ideas of state autonomy and interdependence are inextricably linked to one another and cannot be thought of in isolation.

As the legal basis for participants in investment activities, international investment law regulates foreign investment relations, making it easier for those relations to adapt to changing conditions. Additionally, international investment law contributes to the development of improved forms and methods of providing legal protection through the use of public law and private law methods of regulation. From the perspective of international law, international investment law is of a public nature, its rules are established on the basis of the free and voluntary agreement of the wills of states, and the relationships that are controlled by it have the characteristics of being authoritative.

References:

1. Bogatyrev, A. 'Investment Law' (1992) pp 272.
2. Shumilov, V. 'International Economic Law: textbook' (2003) Phoenix pp 512.
3. Velyaminov, G. 'International Economic Law and Process: textbook' (2004) Clover pp

478.

4. Farkhutdinov, I. 'International Investment Law and Process' (2010) Prospect pp 416.
5. Sornarajah, M. 'The International Law on Foreign Investment' (2021) Cambridge University Press.
6. Boguslavsky, M. 'International private law' (2010) Infra-M pp 704.
7. <https://www.oecd.org/daf/inv/investment-policy/oecdworkoninternationalinvestmentlaw.htm>